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Introducing an indoor object classification dataset including sparse point clouds from mmWave radar

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Abstract

This document introduces the RadIOCD, which is a dataset that contains sparse point cloud representations of indoor objects, collected by subjects wearing a commercial off-the-shelf mmWave radar. In particular, RadIOCD includes the recordings of 10 volunteers moving towards 5 different objects (i.e., backpack, chair, desk, human, and wall), placed in 3 different environments. RadIOCD includes sparse 3D point cloud data, together with their doppler velocity and intensity provided by the mmWave radar. A total of 5,776 files are available, with each one having an approximate duration of 8s. The scope of RadIOCD is the availability of data for the recognition of objects solely recorded by the mmWave radar, to be used in applications where the vision-based classification is cumbersome though critical (e.g., in search and rescue operation where there is smoke inside a building). Furthermore, we showcase that this dataset after being segmented into 76,821 samples contains enough data to apply Machine Learning-based techniques, ensuring that they could generalize in different environments and "unseen" subjects.

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Figures

Fig. 1 The developed device assembled by...

Fig. 2 The selected indoor objects for...

Fig. 3 Visualization of some example point...

Fig. 4 Floor plans of the selected...

id	subject	subprocess	status	url
radio_1	radio_1	radio_1	radio_1	radio_1
radio_2	radio_2	radio_2	radio_2	radio_2
radio_3	radio_3	radio_3	radio_3	radio_3
radio_4	radio_4	radio_4	radio_4	radio_4
radio_5	radio_5	radio_5	radio_5	radio_5
radio_6	radio_6	radio_6	radio_6	radio_6
radio_7	radio_7	radio_7	radio_7	radio_7
radio_8	radio_8	radio_8	radio_8	radio_8
radio_9	radio_9	radio_9	radio_9	radio_9
radio_10	radio_10	radio_10	radio_10	radio_10

Fig. 5 Data organization of RadioCD. The...

Fig. 6 EDA performed on RadioCD, where...

All figures (7)

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